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Evaluation of Student Achievement In Understanding English Language Materials at The Elementary Level In SD 060913: Analysis of Speaking Skills

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Abstrak

The study aims to evaluate students' achievement in understanding English materials at the primary level through the analysis of speaking skills. The results show that students have poor speaking skills, especially in using the right words and correct sentence structure. Teachers need to increase guidance and supervision of students in speaking so that they can improve their speaking skills. The research method used was qualitative with observation and in-depth interview techniques. This research provides recommendations for curriculum development and more effective teaching strategies to improve students' speaking skills at the primary level. As such, this research makes an important contribution to improving the English speaking skills of primary school students through a more focused and targeted approach, and provides a foundation for the development of better education in the future.

Kata kunci: Student Achievement, English, Speaking Skill

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Introduction

Language is a very important tool of human oral communication and oral is the main medium, as is the case with English. English is used as a second language both in the process of formal and non-formal activities. Foreign language learning is found in all levels of education (Wahyu Budi, 2021). English as an international language has an important role in the world of education, including at the elementary school level. English learning in elementary school aims to equip students with basic communication skills in a foreign language, one of which is speaking skills. Speaking skill is an essential aspect of language acquisition as it reflects students' ability to practically apply the linguistic knowledge they have acquired. Evaluation of students' achievement in understanding English materials, especially in speaking skills, is crucial to assess the effectiveness of teaching methods and materials delivered. This analysis can provide an overview of how well students are able to use English in everyday communication contexts, as well as identify areas that require improvement.

English language learning at the primary level plays an important role in improving students' speaking skills. However, there are still many students who have difficulty in speaking well. Poor speaking skills can cause students difficulty in communicating with others, both in formal and informal situations. Therefore, this study aims to generate students' achievement in understanding English materials at the elementary level through the analysis of speaking skills. English learning in primary school has several objectives, such as improving students' speaking, writing and reading skills. However, many teachers still have difficulties in improving students' speaking skills. One way to improve students' speaking skills is by using more interactive and project-based methods. Thus, students can be more active in speaking and improve their speaking skills.

This research also aims to find out how teachers can improve students' speaking skills. One way to improve students' speaking skills is to provide better guidance and supervision. Teachers can provide better guidance and supervision by providing more effective feedback and providing opportunities for students to speak more. This study aims to evaluate students' achievement in understanding English materials at the primary level with a focus on speaking skills. Through this analysis, it is hoped that various factors affecting students' speaking ability can be found, as well as

providing recommendations for curriculum development and more effective teaching strategies. Thus, this study is expected to contribute to the improvement of students' speaking skills at the primary level and improve the quality of English language learning.

METHODS

In this study, the author used qualitative research methods with observation and in-depth interview techniques. The research sample consisted of 21 elementary school students who were purposively selected. Data were collected through observations of students' speaking and in-depth interviews with teachers and students. The data were then analyzed using qualitative data analysis techniques, besides that the author also used the literature study method in making this research article.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

English is one of the most widely that is most widely learned and used in communication between nations. One of the fields that are required to improve their quality in connection with the development of science and science and the flow of information in this age of globalization is the field of language. Mastery of foreign languages, especially English, which is dominant in international relations, is an individual quality that is needed. Mastery of English is an access to achieve success in various fields. The ability of learners to communicate well, both learners' ability to communicate well, both orally and in writing, which aims to improve language skills, thinking and reasoning, and the ability to broaden horizons. Learners are expected to be able to have skills in social interaction and be able to appreciate differences in community life and can appreciate (Zulela, 2020). Literally the word evaluation comes from the English evaluation which means assessment or appraisal. According to the term evaluation is a planned activity to determine the state of an object using an instrument and the results are compared with benchmarks to obtain conclusions (Indah, 2021).

English lessons have four aspects of learning, namely listening, speaking, reading and writing. These four aspects are interrelated with each other. For example, the writing aspect is closely related to the reading aspect; because to be able to write, reading competence is needed first. By reading a lot, one will be good at writing (Naiborhu, 2019). English subject has different characteristics from other subjects. This difference lies in the function of language as a means of communication. In addition to mastery of vocabulary and grammar, it also requires skills in applying them in communication activities, both oral and written (Depdiknas, 2006).

English language learning at the primary school level aims to introduce students to the basics of this foreign language, including speaking skills which are an integral part of communication skills. However, the results of our interviews show that students' English speaking skills are still very poor. The results of this study were obtained through in-depth interviews with 21 students at SD 060913 who were purposively selected. The interview results show that students have very poor speaking skills. Here are some examples of the interview results:

1. "I can't speak English well because I think English is difficult to read" (Student 1).
2. "I don't like English lessons, English seems more difficult than Math" (Student 2).
3. "I can only talk about subjects that I only learn at school" (Student 3).

The interview results show that students have very poor speaking skills. They have difficulties in using the right words and correct sentence structure. In addition, they also have difficulties in talking about other subjects that are not related to the subject matter at school. Analysis of the students' speaking skills showed that they had difficulties in using the right words and correct sentence structure. They also have difficulties in talking about other subjects unrelated to the subject matter at school. This complacency can be caused by several factors, which can be identified as follows:

1. Limitations of Speaking Practice

Students show limitations in English speaking practice in the classroom. Many learning activities still focus on teaching grammar and vocabulary through conventional methods such as lectures and doing worksheets. As a result, opportunities for students to practice speaking in real situations are minimal.

2. Lack of Confidence:

Many students feel insecure when it comes to speaking in English. Fear of making mistakes and lack of encouragement to speak up are the main barriers. This is exacerbated by the lack of an environment that supports the use of English in daily communication outside the classroom.

3. Student Motivation and Interest:

Students' motivation and interest in learning English are also influential. Lack of understanding of the importance of English speaking skills for their future reduces students' enthusiasm in practicing speaking.

This research makes an important contribution to improving primary school students' English language skills through a more focused and targeted approach. With a deeper understanding of students' speaking skills, teachers can design teaching strategies that are more effective and appropriate to students' needs. In addition, the recommendations provided in this study can also serve as a foundation for curriculum development that is more adaptive and responsive to students' needs in understanding English language materials.

Thus, this study not only provides an overview of the condition of students' speaking skills at the elementary level, but also provides direction for the improvement and development of education in the future. With the focus on speaking skills, it is expected that students can be more confident and able to communicate well in English, which is an important skill in the current era of globalization. In addition, this study also provides encouragement for educators to continue improving their teaching methods in order to have a greater positive impact on the English language skills of elementary school students.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the results of this study show that students have very poor speaking skills in English. They have difficulties in using the right words and correct sentence structure, as well as talking about other subjects that are not related to the subject matter at school. Therefore, teachers need to improve the guidance and supervision of students in speaking so that they can improve their speaking skills, in suggestion, teachers need to improve the guidance and supervision of students in speaking. Teachers can provide better guidance and supervision by providing more effective feedback and providing opportunities for students to speak more. In addition, teachers can also use more interactive and project-based methods to improve students' speaking skills.

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